

A NEW METHOD FOR CONVERSION OF AROMATIC CARBOXYLIC ACIDS INTO THE CORRESPONDING ALDEHYDES. PART I

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Ghadiali and Shah's (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 117) new method for conversion of aromatic carboxylic acids into the corresponding aldehydes through N:N'-diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamidines has been systematically studied in detail in case of conversion of benzoic acid into benzaldehyde. Of the two alternative methods used by them for the preparation of N-carbethoxy-N:N'-diphenylbenzamide, the action of ethyl chloroformate on diphenylbenzamide has been found to be more convenient. This method has now been used for reduction of a number of aromatic acids to the corresponding aldehydes, through the corresponding N-carbethoxybenzamidines. The reactions at various stages were found to be quite smooth giving good yields and the method appears to be of general applicability for aromatic acids.

Ghadiali and Shah (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 117) observed that N:N'-diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamide (II) could be reduced by aluminium amalgam in moist ether to a dihydrobenzamide (III) which readily hydrolysed by cold dilute acid to benzaldehyde. This important observation affords a convenient method for the conversion of an aromatic carboxylic acid into the corresponding aldehyde (Ghadiali, Shirsat and Shah, *Curr. Sci.*, 1948, 17, 332).

In the present investigation the new method of Ghadiali and Shah (*loc. cit.*) has been systematically studied in case of the conversion of benzoic acid into benzaldehyde. Benzoic acid through its anilide was converted into N:N'-diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamide (II) by two methods (cf. Ghadiali and Shah, *loc. cit.*): (1) through the condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with sodium salt of phenylurethane, and (2) through the action of ethyl chloroformate on N:N'-diphenylbenzamide (I) obtained by the condensation of benzanilide with aniline (Shah and Sidiki, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1937, 6A, 136).

(I)

(II)

(III)

In the latter condensation of *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine with ethyl chloroformate, a reaction first studied by Ghadiali and Shah, it was observed that the reaction could be successfully conducted in dry ether or in dry acetone as a solvent.

Ghadiali and Shah (*loc. cit.*) prepared *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxybenzamidine (II) for the first time and studied its reactions. Some more reactions of it have now been studied. It was observed that the compound could be distilled under reduced pressure without decomposition. Ghadiali and Shah who attempted distillation at ordinary pressure observed that it decomposed to *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine. An attempt to prepare a picryl derivative resulted in the formation of aniline picrate. An attempt to condense the compound with aniline with a view to obtaining *N*-(phenyliminobenzyl)-*N:N'*-diphenylurea (cf. Ichaporia and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 431) resulted instead in the formation of *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and *sym*-diphenylurea. The result may be explained by assuming that the desired condensation product, probably formed in the reaction mixture, further reacts with one more mole of aniline to give rise to these two products.

Sidiki and Shah (*loc. cit.*) who condensed *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxycinnamidine with aniline obtained only *sym*-diphenylurea.

The *N*-carbethoxybenzamidine (II) could easily be reduced to *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (III) by aluminium amalgam using moist ether or preferably moist ethyl acetate as a solvent. The reductions with stannous chloride in dry ether or metallic sodium in absolute methyl alcohol were unsuccessful. The dihydro compound (III) was found to be highly unstable, being easily hydrolysed to aldehyde on heating with water or preferably in dilute hydrochloric acid. Even during the reduction some dihydro compound got hydrolysed giving benzaldehyde. An attempt at benzoylating the dihydrobenzamidine resulted in the formation of benzaldehyde and benzanilide, while one at acetylation resulted in its hydrolysis to benzaldehyde and phenylurethane.

As out of the two above methods of conversion, the one through *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and its *N*-carbethoxy derivative was found to be more convenient, it was applied for conversion of several substituted benzoic acids into the corresponding aldehydes.

Thus, *o*-chlorobenzoic acid through *o* chlorobenzanilide was converted into *N:N'*-diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamidine, which condensed with ethyl chloroformate to give *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxy-*o*-chlorobenzamidine. The latter on reduction with aluminium amalgam and subsequent hydrolysis of the dihydrobenzamidine obtained, furnished *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde; *meta*- and *para*-bromobenzoic acids through *N:N'*-diphenyl-*m*- and *p*-bromobenzamidines gave the corresponding *N*-carbethoxybenzamidines. On

reduction the *m*-bromobenzamidine gave a *dihydro* product which hydrolysed to the aldehyde. The *p*-bromobenzamidine derivative, however, gave directly *para*-bromobenzaldehyde, the dihydrobenzamidine being not isolated.

Similarly the anilides of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluic acids gave through the respective N:N'-diphenyltoluamidines the corresponding N-carbethoxytoluamidines. The *o*- and *m*-toluamidines on reduction gave directly the aldehydes; while the *para* derivative furnished the dihydrotoluamidine which hydrolysed to give *p*-tolualdehyde.

In all these cases of conversion, the reactions at various stages were found to be quite smooth giving good yields and the method appears to be of general applicability for aromatic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamidine (II).—(i). Sodium salt of phenylurethane (from 5 g. sodium and 26 g. of phenylurethane) was refluxed with benzanilide imidochloride (30 g.) in dry ether for 12 hours according to Ghadiali and Shah (*loc. cit.*). The reaction product obtained as a yellow paste did not solidify and hence it was distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction at 230°-250°/20 mm. could be crystallised from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum in prismatic needles, m.p. 86-87°, yield 12 g. (Ghadiali and Shah, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 85-87°).

(ii). To a solution of N:N'-diphenylbenzamidine (I) (1 g., 1 mol) in dry benzene (10 c.c.) was added ethyl chloroformate (0.4 g., 1 mol.) dissolved in dry benzene (1 c.c.) with cooling in a freezing mixture and the reaction mixture kept overnight at 0°. It was filtered and on removal of benzene from the filtrate a yellow paste was obtained which was washed with light petroleum (60°-80°) and the solid obtained crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 86°, yield 0.6 g.

Similar results were obtained by using sodium bicarbonate as used by Ghadiali and Shah. It was also observed that replacement of benzene by dry acetone did not affect the yield, while use of higher temperatures diminished the yield.

Reactions of N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamidine (II).—(i). The benzamidine (II) could be distilled undecomposed at 220°/3 mm. (cf. Ghadiali and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

(ii). An attempt to prepare a picrate of the benzamidine (II) in hot alcoholic solution resulted in the formation of aniline picrate, m.p. 189-90°, hydrolysis having taken place.

(iii). The benzamidine (II, 1.5 g.) and aniline (1 g.) were heated at 180° for 4 hours, when the reaction product on crystallisation from alcohol gave *sym*-diphenylurea (carbanilide), m.p. 238-39° and N:N'-diphenylbenzamidine (I), m.p. 141°.

Reduction of N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamidine (II) to N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (III). Aluminium amalgam.—The usual methods

given in literature did not give satisfactory results, hence it was prepared as follows: Aluminium wire (0.05 cm. dia., 7.0 g.) was cut into pieces of about 8 to 10 cm. in length, and each piece rolled into a small coil. They were then washed with ether, acetone and water; treated with sodium hydroxide solution (5%) for about two minutes and then with hydrochloric acid (5%) and finally washed with plenty of water. After thorough washing, the coils dipped in water (10 c.c.) were treated with solid mercuric chloride (1 g.) and the flask shaken with cooling if necessary. When all the mercuric chloride went in solution more water was added and then the contents washed. Most of the water was decanted off keeping about 10 c.c. and mercuric chloride (1 g.) was again added and the process repeated twice, till the aluminium coils were coated with sufficient amount of mercury. The coils were thoroughly washed with water till free of mercuric chloride, then with ether and directly used.

To a freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (16 g.) a solution of N:N'-diphenyl-N-carbethoxybenzamidine (II, 2 g.) in moist ether (alcohol-free ether to which were added 2 or 3 drops of water, 200 c.c.) was added. The amalgam reacted vigorously liberating tiny bubbles of hydrogen. After 20 minutes, the solution was filtered and the ether distilled off. The solid that remained was crystallised from a mixture of petroleum and benzene as colorless glistening needles, m.p. 103°, yield 1.5 g. (Ghadiali and Shah, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 104-106°).

Similar yields were obtained when moist ethyl acetate was used as a solvent; the reduction being more vigorous in this case, the reaction period was only 15 minutes.

The original benzamidine (II) was recovered unchanged when the reduction was attempted with stannous chloride in ethereal suspension and passing hydrogen chloride under anhydrous conditions. Attempted reduction of the benzamidine (II) in methyl alcoholic solution by metallic sodium resulted in the formation of N:N'-diphenylbenzamidine (I).

Reactions of N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (III). (i) *Hydrolysis.*—The dihydrobenzamidine (2 g.) was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.), well stirred and a further quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) added. It was well shaken, warmed on a water-bath, cooled and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried, ether removed and the brownish oil (0.4 g.) that remained was identified as benzaldehyde by preparing its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. with one prepared from benzaldehyde, 258° (Curtius and Dedischen, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1894, *ii*, 50, 264, give m.p. 235°).

(ii). Attempted benzoylation of the dihydrobenzamidine (0.5 g.) by benzoyl chloride (1 c.c.) in a solution of sodium hydroxide (10%, 5 c.c.) gave benzaniide, m.p. 160°, and benzaldehyde.

(iii). Attempted acetylation of the dihydrobenzamidine (0.5 g.) with fused sodium acetate (0.4 g.) and acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) by heating on a water-bath for half an hour gave phenylurethane, m.p. 52° (after crystallisation from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) and benzaldehyde.

N:N'-Diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamide.—*o*-Chlorobenzanilide (m. p. 115°; 15 g.) and aniline (7 g.) were mixed and phosphorus oxychloride (100 c. c.) slowly added when a vigorous reaction occurred. It was heated in an oil-bath at 140°-150° for 5 hours, cooled, then slowly added to cold water (200 c. c.) and the solid obtained was collected. The solid was triturated with strong ammonium hydroxide and then this heated for half an hour. *N:N'*-diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamide that separated was collected, washed and crystallised from alcohol as colorless needles, m. p. 130°, yield 15 g. (Found: Cl, 12.0. C₁₉H₁₃N₂Cl requires Cl, 11.5 per cent). It is soluble in EtOH, MeOH and acetone and less soluble in benzene and light petroleum.

The hydrochloride was obtained as prismatic needles, m. p. 297-98°. (Found: Cl, 20.8. C₁₉H₁₃N₂Cl.HCl requires Cl, 20.7 per cent).

The picrate was prepared as shining yellow needles, m.p. 201-202°. (Found: Cl, 6.3. C₂₃H₁₅O₇N₃Cl requires Cl, 6.6 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxy-*o*-chlorobenzamide.—To a solution of *N:N'*-diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamide (15 g.) in dry benzene (200 c. c.) containing sodium bicarbonate (10.2 g.), ethyl chloroformate (4.8 g.) was slowly added with cooling in a freezing mixture. After keeping the reaction mixture overnight at 0°, it was filtered and benzene removed from the filtrate when a yellow paste was obtained. The paste after washing with light petroleum (60°-80°) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining white needles (8.0 g.), m. p. 169-70°. (Found: Cl, 9.6. C₂₃H₁₉O₂N₂Cl requires Cl, 9.4 per cent). The condensation was also carried out using ethyl acetate as a solvent with good results. It is sparingly soluble in petroleum, moderately in benzene and alcohol, and easily in chloroform.

The benzamide (0.5 g.) when refluxed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide gave *N:N'*-diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamide.

The benzamide (0.5 g.) was heated with aniline (2 g.) at 180°-190° for 3½ hours when *sym*-diphenylurea, m. p. 242°, and *N:N'*-diphenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamide, m. p. 130°, were formed.

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxydihydro-*o*-chlorobenzamide.—The above *N*-carbethoxybenzamide (1.5 g.) in moist ethereal solution (200 c. c.) was added to aluminium amalgam (13 g.), and the reaction mixture was just warmed to start the reaction and kept aside. After about 20 minutes, it was filtered and the ether removed. The yellowish paste that remained was washed with light petroleum (20 c. c.) and crystallised from a mixture of light (b. p. 60°-80°) and heavy petroleum (b.p. 100°-120°) when *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxydihydro-*o*-chlorobenzamide separated in shining needles, m.p. 108-109°. (Found: Cl, 9.5. C₂₂H₂₁O₂N₂Cl requires Cl, 9.3 per cent). A good yield was obtained when reduction was carried out in moist ethyl acetate as a solvent.

The above dihydrobenzamide (2 g.) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid when *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, b.p. 210°-212° (0.4 g.) was obtained (Mayer and English, *Annalen*, 1918, 417, 78, give b.p. 213°-214°). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. with one prepared from an authentic specimen of *o*-chlorobenzal-

dehyde, 211-12°. (Found: Cl, 11.5. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9O_2N_2$: Cl, 11.1 per cent). (Campbell, *Analyst*, 1936, 61, 391, gives m.p. 206°).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*m*-bromobenzamidine was prepared as the corresponding *o*-chlorobenzamidine from *m*-bromobenzanilide (m.p. 148°; 35.0 g.), aniline (25.0 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (200 c.c.) and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as tiny colorless needles (38.0 g.), m.p. 132°. (Found: Br, 22.8. $C_{19}H_{13}N_2Br$ requires Br, 22.8 per cent). The hydrochloride was obtained as shining plates, m.p. 262°. (Found: hal., 29.6. $C_{19}H_{13}N_2Br.HCl$ requires hal., 29.8 per cent). The picrate, was obtained as yellow needles, m. p. 192°. (Found: Br, 13.4. $C_{25}H_{15}O_7N_5Br$ requires Br, 13.7 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxy-*m*-bromobenzamidine was prepared from the above benzamidine (10.0 g.) by condensation with ethyl chloroformate (3.0 g.) in benzene solution in presence of sodium bicarbonate (8.0 g.) in prisms from a mixture of benzene and petroleum, m.p. 88-90°, yield 6.0 g. (Found: Br, 19.0. $C_{22}H_{15}O_2N_2Br$ requires Br, 18.9 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxydihydro-*m*-bromobenzamidine.—The above *N*-carbethoxybenzamidine (2.0 g.) in moist ethereal solution was reduced with aluminium amalgam (20 g.) for 15 minutes at room temperature. The residue after washing with light petroleum (b.p. 60°-80°) was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum in colorless glistening needles, m.p. 108°. (Found: Br, 18.8. $C_{22}H_{21}O_2N_2Br$ requires Br, 18.8 per cent).

The dihydrobenzamidine (1.5 g.) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to give *m*-bromobenzaldehyde (0.3 g.), b.p. 230°-233° (Mettler, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2810, gives b.p. 228°-230°/726 mm.). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared as needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. 251-52°.

N:N'-Diphenyl-*p*-bromobenzamidine was prepared from *p*-bromobenzanilide (m. p. 198-99°; 20 g.), aniline (13 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (80 c.c.) in needles from benzene and heavy petroleum (22 g.), m.p. 175°. The hydrochloride was prepared as prisms from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 292° (decomp.). (Found: hal., 30.1. $C_{19}H_{15}N_2Br.HCl$ requires hal., 30.1 per cent). The picrate was prepared in yellow needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 194°. (Found: Br, 13.1. $C_{25}H_{15}O_7N_5Br$ requires Br, 13.7 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxy-*p*-bromobenzamidine was prepared by the condensation of the above benzamidine (20 g.) with ethyl chloroformate (6 g.) in presence of sodium bicarbonate (10 g.) in benzene as prisms from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum, m.p. 107°, yield 11 g. (Found: Br, 18.8. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_2Br$ requires Br, 18.9 per cent).

Reduction of N:N'-Diphenyl-*N*-carbethoxy-*p*-bromobenzamidine.—The reduction of the benzamidine (2 g.) was carried out with aluminium amalgam (20 g.) in moist ether (200 c.c.). As no solid dihydro product could be isolated from the product obtained on removal of ether, it was directly hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid when *p*-bromobenzaldehyde was obtained as needles, m.p. 56-57°, yield 0.3 g. (Adams and

Vollweiler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 1738, give m.p. 56-57°. 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as red needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. 256-57°.

N:N'-Diphenyl-*o*-toluamidine was prepared from *o*-toluanilide (m.p. 130°; 30 g.), aniline (14.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (120 g.) as long white needles from alcohol, m.p. 126-27°, yield 36 g. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

The hydrochloride was obtained as needles from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 290-92°. (Found: Cl, 11.1. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 11.0 per cent). The picrate was obtained as yellow prisms from methyl alcohol, m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{28}H_{21}O_7N_5$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxy-*o*-toluamidine was prepared from the above *o*-toluamidine (10 g.), ethyl chloroformate (3 g.) and sodium bicarbonate (8 g.) in benzene as white prismatic needles from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 145°, yield 6 g. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 6.8; N, 8.1. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.7; H, 6.1; N, 7.8 per cent).

Reduction N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxy-*o*-toluamidine.—The above N-carbethoxytoluamidine (2 g.) was reduced with aluminium amalgam (20 g.), the dihydro compound was not isolated but the reaction product was directly hydrolysed to *o*-tolualdehyde, b.p. 200° (Bornemann, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 1467, gives b.p. 199°-200°). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, orange-red needles, m.p. 193-94° (Nauta, Ernsting and Faber, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1941, **60**, 915, m.p. 193-94°).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*m*-toluamidine was prepared from *m*-toluanilide (m.p. 133°; 15 g.), aniline (7 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (45 c.c.) in tiny needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 117°, yield 13.5 g. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

The hydrochloride was prepared as plates from alcohol, m. p. 265°. (Found: Cl, 10.9. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 11.0 per cent). The picrate as yellow needles from methyl alcohol, m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{28}H_{21}O_7N_5$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxy-*m*-toluamidine was obtained when the above toluamidine (10 g.) was condensed with ethyl chloroformate (3 g.) in presence of sodium bicarbonate (8 g.) in benzene, as prisms from alcohol, m.p. 86°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 5.4; N, 8.0. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.7; H, 6.1; N, 7.8 per cent).

Reduction of N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxy-*m*-toluamidine.—The above N-carbethoxytoluamidine (2 g.) was reduced with aluminium amalgam (20 g.) and the reduction product without isolation was hydrolysed to *m*-tolualdehyde, b.p. 201° (Gundeloh, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1876, *ii*, **26**, 44, b.p. 199°).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as orange needles, m. p. 207°. (Found: N, 18.4. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_4$ requires N, 18.7 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*p*-toluamidine was prepared from *p*-toluanilide (m.p. 147°; 30 g.), aniline (14 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (120 g.) as needles from alcohol, m.p. 170°, yield 35 g. (Found: N, 9.7. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{18}N_2$: N, 9.8 per cent) (Glock, *Ber.*, 1898, **21**, 2665, m.p. 168°). The hydrochloride was obtained as plates from acetic acid, m.p.

272° (Found : Cl, 10.8. $C_{26}H_{18}N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 11.0 per cent) and the *picrate*, as yellow needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 210° (Found : N, 13.6. $C_{26}H_{21}O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

N:N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxy-p-toluamide was prepared from the above toluamide (15 g.), ethyl chloroformate (5.6 g.) and sodium bicarbonate (12 g.) and crystallised from alcohol as colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 115-16°, yield 6.0 g. (Found : C, 77.0 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 8.0. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.7 ; H, 6.1 ; N, 7.8 per cent).

N.N'-Diphenyl-N-carbethoxydihydro-p-toluamide was obtained when the above N-carbethoxytoluamide (1.0 g.) was reduced with aluminium amalgam (8 g.) as white shining needles from petroleum and benzene mixture, m.p. 114-15°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : N, 7.5. $C_{23}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.8 per cent).

It was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid when *p*-tolualdehyde, b.p. 204°-208° was obtained (Bornemann, *loc. cit.*, b.p. 204-205°). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as red needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. and mixed m.p., 230° (Nauta, Ernsting and Faber, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 235°).

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